

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPACT DUAL-BAND PATCH ANTENNA FOR WIFI COMMUNICATION AT 2.45 GHZ AND 5 GHZ

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Abstract – This study explores the application of an alternative design in a patch antenna for Wi-Fi network frequencies. Wi-Fi is responsible for connecting essential electronic devices in modern life, operating in the 2.45 and 5 GHz bands, which are essential to ensure the performance and stability of wireless networks, enabling high transmission speeds and lower latency. Initially, we designed an antenna for the 2.45 GHz frequency, calculating its dimensions using the SciLab software. We then implemented and analyzed the project using the 3D electromagnetic simulator, Ansys HFSS. We tested various antenna designs and shapes to cover both frequencies, and these tests highlighted the potential of one antenna in particular, which demonstrated successful operation in both requested frequency bands.

Key-Words: Patch Antenna, Wi-Fi Communication, Dual Band, Ansys HFSS.

INTRODUCTION

In today's landscape, wireless communication plays a crucial role in various applications, ranging from home networks to industrial systems. Among the most widely used technologies, Wi-Fi stands out for its ability to provide fast and efficient connectivity in different environments. Wi-Fi operates on two main frequencies: 2.45 GHz, which offers greater range with moderate speeds, and 5 GHz, which provides higher speeds over shorter distances [1]. Traditionally, communication devices use separate antennas for each of these frequencies, which can lead to increased complexity and additional costs.

According to the *IEEE Standard Definitions of Terms for Antennas* [2], an antenna is a means of transmitting or receiving radio waves. In other words, an antenna is a structure that facilitates the transition between free space and a guiding device, responsible for carrying electromagnetic wave energy from a transmitting source to the antenna or from the antenna to a receiver [3]. Antennas come in various shapes and types, such as Wire Antennas, Aperture Antennas, Microstrip Antennas, Array Antennas, Reflector Antennas, Lens Antennas, and many others [4].

In this context, patch antennas, a class of Microstrip antennas, emerge as a promising solution. These antennas consist of a patch made of a metallic material, in this case copper, on a grounded substrate. Their advantages include being low-profile, functional on both planar and non-planar surfaces, simple, and cost-effective to manufacture, as they use printed circuit technology. Additionally, they can operate over a wide range of frequencies.

That said, this study proposes the development of a compact patch antenna that can operate simultaneously on both Wi-Fi frequencies, aiming to simplify device design and enhance communication efficiency.

DEVELOPMENT

Initially, we designed a conventional patch antenna for the frequency of 2.45 GHz. For this, we used the code of the Sci-Lab program developed by the Maxwell Laboratory of Microwave and Applied Electromagnetism, available in [5], which calculates the essential parameters of the antenna, such as dimensions, impedance and dielectric constant of the substrate. We chose FR4 material for the substrate, which has a dielectric constant of 4.3 and a height of 1.6 mm, with an input impedance of 50 Ω , making it ideal for microstrip applications. In figure 1, we can analyze all the results obtained, as well as the initial design of the antenna.

Figure 1 – Antenna Parameters.

After defining the initial dimensions, we modeled the antenna using the Ansys HFSS simulator, an advanced tool for 3D electromagnetic simulation.

This step was crucial for us to evaluate the performance of the antenna in terms of return parameters (S parameters), gain and directivity.

Once we modeled the dimensions of the antenna, we tested various shapes and configurations to optimize its response at both frequencies (2.5 and 5 GHz). The goal was not only to achieve better performance of the S-parameter at the two desired frequencies, but also to ensure that the radiation pattern was uniform, without significant discrepancies.

The design process involved several iterations. In the first iteration, shown in figure 2, the S parameter was very close to the desired target, with frequencies of 2.71 GHz and 5.3 GHz.

Figure 2 – First iteration.

In addition to the frequencies of interest, we include the graph that shows all the frequencies reached in figure 3, the data in the graph are shown in Table 1.

Figure 3 – S Parameter for the first iteration.

TABLE 1 – Results of Parameter S in Plot 1.

	Frequencies (GHz)	Gain (dB)
M1	2.71	-10.26
M2	3.67	-20.52
M3	5.32	-19.89
M4	7.72	-22.79

Note: M1, M2, M3 and M4 are the points where the frequencies perform optimally.

We observed that the directivity of the antenna exhibited a "break" in the middle, as shown in figure 4, resulting in two lobes of radiation. This result was undesirable for the proposed request. While having two lobes in one antenna may be advantageous in other applications, this is not the case in this study. The proper result is to achieve a

uniform directivity response, ensuring that the Wi-Fi network maintains a consistent connection distance to the device, regardless of the frequency used, allowing the connected device to operate at the same distance from the modem.

Figure 4 – Directivity of the first iteration, with 5 GHz.

To solve this problem, we devised a new design that incorporated side notches in the patch, allowing electromagnetic waves to concentrate in the center of the antenna, as shown in figure 5. This modification aimed to create a more homogeneous radiation pattern, which is essential to ensure consistent coverage at both frequencies.

Figure 5 – Second iteration.

First, we analyzed the gain parameter for this design, as shown in Figure 6, table 2 shows your data.

Figure 6 – S parameter for the second iteration.

TABLE 2 – Results of Parameter S in Plot 2.

	Frequencies (GHz)	Gain (dB)
M1	2.44	-9.77
M2	3.67	-31.84
M3	5.34	-26,89
M4	7.84	-41.00
M5	8.82	-29.66

Note: M1, M2, M3, M4 and M5 are the points where the frequencies perform optimally.

Subsequent simulations showed satisfactory gain in three frequencies: 2.44 GHz, 3.67 GHz, and 5.34 GHz. Although the 5.34 GHz frequency is slightly above the desired range, the Wi-Fi bandwidth allows for a margin of safety, making performance acceptable.

Additionally, the directivity of the antenna has improved significantly, with the new configuration resulting in a more concentrated central lobe and a reduction in the lateral lobes, as we see in figure 7.

Figure 7 – Directivity of the second iteration, with 5 GHz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained in the simulations demonstrated a satisfactory performance, meeting the objectives set at the beginning of the study. The projected antenna exhibited resonances at 2.44 GHz, 3.67 GHz, and 5.34 GHz, as evidenced by the S-parameters obtained in the simulations. The proximity of the 2.44 GHz frequency to the target 2.45 GHz frequency (with a difference of only 0.01 GHz) is particularly encouraging, as it indicates that with the proper adjustments the antenna can operate efficiently in this operating range.

The S-parameter, which measures the power reflection in the antenna, presented values close to the ideal, indicating a good adaptation of the antenna to the operating frequencies. The analysis of the S-parameter graph in figure 6 revealed that the antenna maintains a low reflection rate, crucial to ensure efficiency in signal transmission and reception. The directivity of the antenna, shown in figure 7, has improved significantly with the new design that incorporated side notches. Uniformity of the radiation pattern is essential to ensure consistent Wi-Fi coverage, allowing users to benefit from a stable connection at various distances from the modem.

Although the results were satisfactory, we observed that the posterior lobe still exhibited considerable radiation. Therefore, future design

iterations should focus on minimizing this unwanted radiation, either through further adjustments to the patch format or the implementation of radiation mitigation techniques.

To validate the theoretical data, experimental confirmation of the results will be required, specifically by fabricating the antenna using a printed circuit board. The physical construction of the antenna is a crucial step in confirming the effectiveness of the design under real operating conditions and in conducting other performance tests that can provide additional data on efficiency and quality of communication.

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